

ANDRÉ MASSON'S "EULOGY OF PAUL KLEE"

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SUMMARY

This paper aims to clarify how André Masson, a Surrealist painter, understands Paul Klee's art and how Masson and Klee intersect. Masson's essay "Eulogy of Paul Klee" (1946) demonstrates his viewpoints: Klee transgresses conventional value judgments and creates open pictorial space in his paintings, turning his back on the perspective as a traditional representation system and using materials and techniques in a unique way in his creative process. In addition, his works often have archaic tones. In them, Masson finds Klee's con-

cept of time, which is neither linear nor chronological, and he indicates this by coining the term "infinir," meaning "let it never end." Masson cites Klee and the "romantics of the North" as those who desire to "infinir" – a longing Masson shares with them. He projects onto Klee his idea that an artwork should be dynamic and transformative, not static or fixed. Masson never met Klee, but drawings by both were illustrated in an edition of the German Romantic poet Novalis's *The Novices of Sais* published in 1949.

INTRODUCTION

André Masson (1896–1987) is a French artist 17 years younger than Paul Klee. André Breton, the same age as Masson, named the two artists as having Surrealist qualities in his *Surrealist Manifesto* (1924).¹ Klee has since come to be regarded as a precursor in Surrealist plastic arts, although he never joined the movement.² On the other hand, Masson participated in Surrealism during two periods, in the late 1920s and the late 1930s, and then definitely parted company with Breton while in exile in the United States during World War II. Since then, he was often critical of "orthodox" surrealist painters like Salvador Dalí, while he continued calling himself a Surrealist. He harboured ambivalent feelings toward the movement.

Masson and Klee did not meet directly. The Surrealist movement did not play a role in bringing them together. Masson discovered Klee's works before he joined the movement, and later, when he distanced himself from it, he wrote an essay titled "Eulogy of Paul Klee" in 1946. For Masson, certainly, Klee must have been a crucial artist of his time. It seems unfortunate that the two artists did not have the opportunity to interact. Their works were sometimes shown in the same exhibition, yet were there no further indirect encounters between the two artists?

Through a reflection on Masson's essay on Klee, this article explores the artistic concepts of Klee which Masson identified and the possible intersections between the two artists.

ENCOUNTER WITH KLEE'S WORK

Masson discovered Klee's works in 1922³ or 1923⁴ before the Surrealism movement was formed. He worked in a shabby studio on Rue Blomet in Paris, with Joan Miró in an adjoining studio just one wall away.⁵ The two young artists were looking for a new style of painting that could break free from conventions. The challenge for artists was ridding themselves of Cubism's influence. At this time, the two of them came across the work of Klee. "Together, Masson and I, we discovered Paul Klee, an essential discovery for both of us,"⁶ testifies Miró. He also remarks:

"I'm grateful to André Masson above all for having introduced me to the painting of Paul Klee. One day when he showed me some plates in one of his albums ... I was overwhelmed! I dashed to the only gallery in Paris that showed his gouaches and watercolours. From that day on, my work took an entirely different course, and it became surrealist, if that's the term you want to use. My encounter with Klee's work was the most important event in my life. My painting was freed from all earthly bonds by his influence. Klee enabled me to realize that a single spot, a spiral, even a dot, could form the subject of a painting, just as much as a face, a landscape, or a monument ..."⁷

The plates that Masson showed to Miró have been identified⁸: They can be found in the monograph *Kairuan oder eine Geschichte vom Maler Klee und von der Kunst dieses Zeitalters* (1921).⁹ This monograph contains many monochromatic drawings and several colour paintings, including watercolours with Klee's original technique: oil transfer drawing.¹⁰ For the two young artists of that period, this must have been one of the few opportunities to observe Klee's works in colour, even if they were printed reproductions. The gallery that Miró mentions is probably the Vavin-Raspail Gallery, which opened at the end of 1924 and was the only gallery in Paris that dealt with Klee's works at the time.¹¹

As the artist admits, the encounter with Klee's works brought about a significant change in Miró's creative process around 1925. In his previous work, Miró had set the motifs in front of him and had represented them with "meticulous workmanship" to give the surface of the canvas "an enamel-like smoothness and density."¹² After his discovery of Klee's works, he freed himself from the motifs, spread watercolour-like washes all over the canvas, and painted with extra thin strokes and signs that functioned as sym-

Fig. 1

André Masson, *Automatic drawing [Dessin automatique] "Quare de vulva eduxistime"*, 1923, ink on paper, 26.5 x 20 cm, printed in: Florence de Mèredieu, *André Masson. Les dessins automatiques*, Paris: Blusson, 1988, p. 89

bols. Some studies on Miró demonstrate the influence of Klee through comparative analyses of the two artists' works.¹³ However, the influence of Klee on Masson's works is not as clear as it is in the case of Miró. Moreover, Masson has not professed an influence from Klee as directly as Miró has in his discourse. Nevertheless, if we were to make a hypothesis, it would be that Masson saw in Klee's drawings a breakthrough from Cubism. When he discovered Klee, Masson was experimenting with pen and ink drawings to escape from the laws of Cubism. It was an attempt to derive some forms from the accumulation of scribble-like lines that were the traces of the movements of the artist's hand, and eventually came to be called "automatic drawing" (FIG.1). Masson might have been encouraged to experiment with this drawing technique after carefully observing Klee's various drawings in *Kairuan*.¹⁴ Nevertheless, there is little evidence available to prove the hypothesis. Therefore, we will base our conclusions on Masson's essay to understand what he found in Klee's art.

ARTISTIC CONCEPTS OF KLEE WHICH MASSON IDENTIFIED IN HIS ESSAY

Non-Perspective, Unlimited Pictorial Space

There are two texts that Masson wrote about Klee. The first is "Eulogy of Paul Klee,"¹⁵ published in the revue *Fontaine* in 1946, six years after Klee passed away. It is in response to the critical essay "Paul Klee, or Passivity"¹⁶ by René Renne and Claude Serbanne in the *Cahiers du Sud* the previous year. The second is a part of the literary fragmented text titled "Aesthetic moralities – Leaves in the wind"¹⁷ for *La Nouvelle Revue Française* in 1959, in which Masson mentions Klee's art in a simple yet pertinent way, along with discussions on the art of Rembrandt, Redon, Van Gogh and Blake as well as his interest in the East, including Zen and Taoism.

Since the two texts were written years later, we do not have direct access to Masson's ideas when he discovered Klee's work. However, these texts are a key for us to see what artistic concepts Masson identified in Klee's work. Klee's creative theory is considered to have been well established by the 1920s and he maintained it even in his later years, without discontinuity.

Let us now look at Masson's text. In the previous section, we proposed the hypothesis that Masson saw in Klee's drawings the possibility of overcoming Cubism. However, Masson does not explicitly mention Klee's drawings in his text. Instead, he focuses on his pictorial space:

"Henri Michaux writes, not without humor, about the pictures of a school considered till now to be one of the most emancipated as regards servility to the visual, and says: 'We all know that you can't see more than ten feet into them.' With Paul Klee, the exact contrary is the case, what he seeks is the unlimited. From 1912 on, finding himself with a desire to render the *infinite* [= *infinir*], (the same desire characterizes the Chinese and also certain primitives [= romantics¹⁸] of the North, with whom he is connected by his origins), he wants to hold in check the too reasonable horizon. The slight antenna of a scarab will suffice to measure the desert, and the trail of a gust of pollen will humiliate the Milky Way."¹⁹

The quotation from Michaux characterizes the space surrounding the represented objects, whether a still life or a figure, as limited in Cubist paintings.²⁰ The viewers find in them only an area of about three meters and see no further. Masson identifies the year 1912 as a turning point, and this is probably because in this year Klee joined the second exhibition of the "Blue Rider" (der Blaue Reiter) or because the Synthetic Cubism, in which Klee never took part, had been established then. Masson states that Klee de-

sires to suppress the “too reasonable horizon,” citing “Chinese” and “certain primitives [= romantics] of the North” as those who share the same desire as Klee: “a desire to render the *infinite* [= *infinir*].” Masson is not satisfied with the existing words and coins a new French word “infinir” by adding the negative prefix “in-” to the verb “finir”, that is, “to let it never end.”

The “rational horizon” refers to logical and intellectual thoughts. When Klee sometimes paints intentionally like a child,²¹ it is probably due to his rejection of a world backed by logic and knowledge. In addition, the “too reasonable horizon” could be interpreted as the horizon represented in the paintings. In other words, it refers to the rationality of perspective as a representation system that transforms a three-dimensional space into a two-dimensional painting. By ignoring the perspective, Klee tries to discredit the “too reasonable horizon.” Indeed, Klee wrote in his diary: “Perspective makes me yawn.”²² Even if Cubism can be said to be an approach that relativizes perspective in paintings, its pictorial space is too narrow. Klee does not follow cubistic rules because he wishes to create a different pictorial space. Thus, Masson argues that Klee rejects the “too reasonable horizon” and contemplates a non-perspective and unlimited pictorial space.

Smallness and Energy

When evaluating the expanse of Klee’s painting space, which is “irrational” due to neither traditional perspective nor the narrow space of the Cubists, Masson contrasts “the desert” with “a scarab,” and “the Milky Way” with “a gust of pollen,” that is, the vast and the minute. Is this merely an expression of poetic association? Here, Masson states that the minute outweighs the vast. In other words, Masson sees that Klee gives the advan-

tage to the small. He also states the following about the size of Klee’s work:

“The critics when writing of Klee are generally embarrassed. Preferring to avoid him, some go to the length of basing their arguments on the restricted size of his works, and of claiming that ‘they’re nothing but postage stamps.’ But it so happens that Klee, who has nothing to hide from us, entitles one of his works, and one of the most characteristic ones: *A Little World*. That argument (of the postage stamp) would be inaccessible to those who think, with William Blake, that there is but a slight relationship between energy and dimension – who are prepared to affirm that the malice of a flea is such that were the evil creature the size of a horse it would be able to ravage the whole of Great Britain.”²³

Masson cites a diminutive work of Klee (FIG. 2), and through an analogy he connects Klee to Blake. Indeed, Blake, too, made a small-sized work about a tiny creature: a flea²⁴ (FIG. 3). For these two painters, dimension is irrelevant; even a creature as small as a flea can have a significant impact. Thus, Masson identifies in Klee’s work a sensitivity to the distinction between energy and size.

Klee’s *Little Cosmos* (*Kleinwelt*, 1914, 120), which Masson mentions, is a zinc plate etching. On a surface measuring 14.4 by 9.6 cm, doodle-like lines and ink blots intricately form what appear to be human figures, small animals, and plants, all crowded together.

Renne and Serbanne also mention this work in their essay: “for example, *A Little World* [= *Cosmos*] (1914) is a sensitive work that reveals a lack of power to fix vision.”²⁵ When confronted with this work, the viewers’ eyes do not focus but glide in various directions across the almost depthless surface of the work. From this point of view, it could be said that this painting is a minimal version of all-over paintings. In addition, despite the accu-

Fig. 3
William Blake, *The Ghost of a Flea*, c. 1819–20,
tempera and gold on mahogany, support:
21.4 × 16.2 cm, Tate, bequeathed by
W. Graham Robertson 1949
© Photo: Tate

Fig. 2
Paul Klee, *Kleinwelt [Little Cosmos]*, 1914, 120,
etching, 14.3 × 9.5 cm, Zentrum Paul Klee,
Bern
© Zentrum Paul Klee, Bern, Image Archive

mulation of lines and blots, most do not come to form concrete figures. Even if we can detect something like a face, we cannot find a body connected to it, or even if we can detect a body, it may look like a stick. Moreover, Renne and Serbanne see in Klee's works even an insistence on "weakness": "He [= Klee] is a veritable reverse caricaturist, capturing in people and things not their line of strength, but their line of weakness."²⁶ Klee takes the characteristics of weakness from his motifs: people and things.

Renne and Serbanne's discussion on Klee appears ambivalent because they use negative terms such as "a lack of power," "powerless," and "weakness". Masson, on the other hand, evaluates Klee more clearly. The word "malice," which Masson associates with a flea, implies hostility or aggressiveness. Masson thinks that, though small-sized, Klee's works have the power to overturn existing values.²⁷ Therefore, he selects the word "energy" to describe this power.

As mentioned above, standing for the idea that energy resides even in small-

ness or weakness, Masson supports the inversion of conventional value judgments found in Klee's work.

An Artwork in Transformation

Regarding Klee's *Little Cosmos*, Masson also notes: "his work most often bears the imprint of the imperial and sacred arts"; "The fact is that Klee's world calls for a full cargo of the past – a very distant past."²⁸ Then Masson cites an anecdote about Brummell, a figure of the 19th-century English Dandyism, who had his ties filed to give a tone of age before he wore them. These discourses suggest that Klee's techniques in his creative process give his works old, aged, or even a decayed appearance.²⁹ Does Masson propose that Klee professes another inversion of value: old and new? The second text of Masson gives us a hint:

"Paul Klee's very fine taste for the *worn-out*, *sandblasted* and *corroded* appearance. His works, so personal, barely out of his hands, he likes them to resemble excavated objects: towards anonymity. His works, so innovative, he wants them to appear to carry the weight of millennia: Two or three thousand years, that's what improves and *rejuvenates* all things.

Variant: Paintings aromatized, macerated, filled with aroma ..."³⁰

Although the characteristics of Klee's unique technique are listed here, what Masson has in mind is not a binary opposition or inversion. His idea is this: Once his work has left his hands, Klee wants it to take on an aspect of the past so distant that it is no longer recognizable as belonging to anyone. He wants his innovative work to look like an archaeological relic.³¹ Yet, Masson mentions, the work does not remain old; it becomes better and younger with time. We find here his insight about a conception of time found in Klee's works³²: non-linear, non-chronological time.³³

Related to the notion of time, Masson also characterizes the transformation of the work in the last line noting that a Klee painting is "aromatized" with flavours and spices, softened through the process of "maceration" (a vocabulary of wine production), and finally "filled with aroma."³⁴ What Masson was trying to describe here is the potentiality of transformation of the work. He does not see the work as a fixed and static object but as something that has the potential to move and transform in time. This concept of transformation might be related to what Masson describes as "energy."

Masson is an artist who resisted stillness and sought to bring something dynamic into his paintings. Klee wrote in his diary, "Ingres is said to have ordered the motionless; I want to go beyond pathos and order motion. (The new Romanticism)."³⁵ These very words overlap with Masson's pictorial explorations.

As we see above, Masson noticed that Klee wants to give his work a specific concept of time. Here is projected Masson's idea that a painting is to be not static or fixed but dynamic and transformative.

Klee's Specific Alchemy

Focusing on Klee's techniques in the creative process, Masson continues as follows:

"And therefore Paul Klee will have recourse to means which are personal, to an alchemy which belongs to him alone; or he will employ the means peculiar to his time in order to express the liberation of space which is ours."³⁶

In a pictorial space free from the traditional perspective or the rules of Cubism, Klee employs a number of techniques of his own. Even if he uses pointillism, it is not Seurat's but Klee's (FIG. 4).³⁷ Masson appreciates the fact that Klee refines the techniques to be unique.

Here is a short list of Klee's techniques and materials in the creative process: a

Fig. 4
Paul Klee, *Klassische Küste* [Classic Coast],
1931, 285, oil on canvas, 80.5 x 68.5 cm,
Staatliche Museen zu Berlin,
Nationalgalerie, Museum Berggruen
© bpk / Nationalgalerie, SMB, Museum
Berggruen / Jens Ziehe

Fig. 5
Paul Klee, *Büsser* [Penitent], 1935, 143,
watercolour and pen on primed burlap;
original frame, 85.5 x 35.5 cm, Zentrum Paul
Klee, Bern
© Zentrum Paul Klee, Bern, Image Archive

variation of materials as support, such as paper (sometimes brushed), canvas, burlap, cardboard, linen, gauze (sometimes applying his unique ground coats with plaster or chalk) (FIG. 5); a usage on the same support of watercolour, gouache, oil, or other different paints; an application of thick or thin coat or spraying of paint with a sieve, and so on. Some of those on this list are deviations from conventional painting production. Will Grohmann, the art critic who has deep knowledge of Klee's art since the Bauhaus period, writes as follows:

"[...] he [= Klee] leaves it [= the technique] to behave as it pleases and, because of his attachment to the technique, abandons its completion in another form. This is exactly the way he works. It is not a matter of chance, but he knowingly takes

advantage of chance. The shortcomings of paper, a fundamental characteristic of painting, unexpectedly lead him to strange whims and inventive ideas."³⁸

Grohmann's point here is that Klee leaves the traces of accidental lines or stains untouched. Klee does not mind unexpected marks on the paper, which are made by the weight of his hand when Klee conducts his technique called oil transfer drawing (FIG. 6). In the same way, he allows dissolved watercolours to spread the stains naturally on the wet paper (FIG. 7). These marks and stains accidentally made are what Masson sees as: "the imprint of the imperial and sacred arts"; "a full cargo of the past – a very distant past."

Taking advantage of chance or accident also applies to Masson's sand paintings

Fig. 6
 Paul Klee, *In der Einöde [In the Wilderness]*,
 1921, 22, oil transfer drawing and
 watercolour on paper on cardboard,
 43.9/44.3 x 27.8/28.1 cm, Zentrum Paul Klee,
 Bern, Livia Klee Donation
 © Zentrum Paul Klee, Bern, Image Archive

Fig. 7
 Paul Klee, *Reife Ernte [Ripe harvest]*, 1924,
 172, ink, wet on wet, pen, watercolour and
 pencil on cardboard, 22.7 x 12.8 cm,
 Sprengel Museum Hannover, Donation
 Sprengel Collection
 © bpk / Sprengel Museum Hannover / Stefan
 Behrens

Fig. 8
 André Masson, *Fish drawn on the sand [Les
 Poissons dessinés sur le sable]*, 1927, oil on
 sand on canvas, 100 x 73 cm, Hermann und
 Margrit Rupf-Stiftung, Kunstmuseum Bern
 © Kunstmuseum Bern

(FIG. 8). Masson conceived the sand paintings around 1926–27 as an extension of automatic drawings. He placed the canvas horizontally and threw liquid glue and sand onto it. Observing the marks and stains accidentally made, in a chaotic aspect beyond the artist's intention, then the artist added some lines and colours. Klee's works with various techniques and Masson's sand painting are based on the different thoughts of each artist. Nevertheless, we can find some affinities: taking advantage of the accidental results, the attachment to the materiality and its texture, and acceptance of the fragile nature of the finished work.³⁹ Therefore in Masson's works might be found the qualities mentioned above in Klee's works and he might well have been inspired or encouraged by them. In any case, the critical point is that Masson's sand paintings and Klee's works are created in a manner that transgresses the conventional painting process.

As Klee hones the techniques until they become uniquely his own, Masson also explores his alchemy. This attitude not only liberates the artists from conventional painting techniques but also leads them to take advantage of accidents in their creative process.

INTERSECTION OF KLEE AND MASSON

Having analytically read Masson's text, we find that Masson identified various artistic concepts of Klee beyond our initial hypothesis. Praising Klee, Masson projects his ideas: the emancipation from conventional values not only on a pictorial level but also on a moral level, the quest for dynamic and transformative energy in the work, and the employment of original techniques taking advantage of accidental results.

Several subsequent developments promoted the dissemination of Masson's essay on Klee. First, in 1950, it was reproduced in Masson's first anthology of art

essays *The Joy of Painting*.⁴⁰ Second, his art dealer, Daniel-Henry Kahnweiler, quoted Masson's words in Klee's monograph published that same year: "A tiny motif – that is what he [= Klee] wanted to grasp. Who then could deny in Klee what André Masson has called his 'princely modesty.'"⁴¹ Also, later that year, the whole of Masson's text was translated into English and published by Curt Valentin in the United States as a booklet with illustrations of Klee's drawings, watercolours, and oil paintings.⁴² It seems to have been a Christmas gift for the gallery's clients, and Masson's text served as an ideal guide to explain Klee's work.

Now a simple question is raised: have the works of the two artists ever appeared on the same stage? In fact, in 1938, the French art magazine *Verve* planned to put Masson, Klee, and Kandinsky together under one publication project. Let us trace the details of this project.

Tériade's Project for *Verve*

Verve is an art and literature magazine founded in December 1937 by the art critic Tériade.⁴³ He began his career at *Cahiers d'Art*, directed by Christian Zervos. He worked for newspapers such as *l'Intransigeant* and *La Bête Noire* and then teamed up with Swiss publisher Albert Skira to publish *Minotaure*. When he launched *Verve*, he was financed generously by an American publishing house. As a result, the magazine luxuriously appears with lithographs printed in renowned workshops such as Fernand Mourlot.

For the second issue to be published on 1 March 1938, Tériade initially had a plan for four artists to each make one lithograph on the theme of celestial bodies: a Comet for Kandinsky, the Sun for Masson, and he proposed Klee to choose a Star or the Moon⁴⁴ (FIG. 9). To get a positive answer from Klee in Bern, Tériade

Fig. 9
Letter from the review *Verve* [E. Tériade] to Paul Klee, 12.01.1938, p. 1, 26.5 x 20.7 cm, Zentrum Paul Klee, Bern, Klee Family Donation, SFK Ko I Par 13
© Zentrum Paul Klee, Bern, Image Archive

Fig. 10.1
Letter from Wassily Kandinsky to Paul Klee, 09.01.1938, p. 1, 26.9 x 20.9 cm, Zentrum Paul Klee, Bern, Klee Family Donation, SFK Ko P Kan 40
© Zentrum Paul Klee, Bern, Image Archive

Fig. 10.2
Letter from Wassily Kandinsky to Paul Klee, 09.01.1938, p. 2, 26.9 x 20.9 cm, Zentrum Paul Klee, Bern, Klee Family Donation, SFK Ko P Kan 40
© Zentrum Paul Klee, Bern, Image Archive

had asked Kandinsky in Paris in advance to give him support. Kandinsky wrote a letter to Klee on 9 January (FIG. 10). He introduces Tériade as a reliable person and one of his “friends.” He also describes *Verve* as an authentic art magazine with numerous illustrations and continues as follows:

“As you can see, I am trying very hard to win you over – and this in the general interest. T. [= Tériade] also told me that at the moment people are becoming more and more interested in the German ‘degenerates’ (finally! – I say). In America, in fact. And that the time of the German artists in America is in the best development. Now let us hope for the best. One does not get full of Parisian interest.”⁴⁵

Kandinsky enthusiastically encourages Klee to join in Tériade’s plan. He invites his comrade to walk with him the path to the American art world together. Since the formation of the Blue Rider (der Blaue Reiter), the two artists had a strong bond; they were colleagues at the Bauhaus and shared the same housing at Dessau. And their work was commonly branded “degenerate art” by the Nazis.

The situation was different for Masson, a French painter of a younger generation. He might have been pleased to participate in the same project as more established artists such as Klee and Kandinsky. More-

over, the theme of the Sun was a part of his emblem. However, for him, working for *Verve* meant mending his relationship with Tériade. Masson was not actively featured in the 1930s in the media that Tériade directed, despite this critic looking at the artist favourably from the late 1920s as one of the younger generation of artists to follow Picasso. The magazine *Minotaure* that he launched in 1933 with Skira did not feature Masson prominently, even though the artist and Georges Bataille were the godparents of the magazine’s name. Having seen the contributions of Breton, Paul Éluard, and Salvador Dalí, frustrated Masson,⁴⁶ who came to believe he was being cold-shouldered by Tériade.

On the other hand, in truth, Tériade did not have a smooth road. In *Minotaure*, Breton and the Orthodox Surrealists’ intervention became increasingly pronounced, and they intended to exclude the “dissidents.” Tériade struggled to reconcile the two factions, and eventually, he withdrew from *Minotaure* at the end of 1936. *Verve* was to be a new start for the art critic, and he quit collaborating with Breton and his associates instead endeavouring to work with Masson and Bataille. He proposed a project that Masson would undoubtedly be satisfied with, giving a place for his lithograph to

appear alongside those of Klee and Kandinsky, with a text by Bataille, who is “always faithful”⁴⁸ to Masson.

However, we now find no lithographs by Klee in the second issue of *Verve*. In addition to the text titled “Celestial bodies” by Bataille, Kandinsky represents Comets and Stars, and Masson the Sun and the Moon. The reason why Klee did not participate in the project has not been identified, but given his illness at the time, it is assumed that it would have been difficult for him to create a new work and send it to Paris in the limited time available.

Novalis's *The Novices of Sais*

As mentioned above, the collaboration between Klee and Masson in the art magazine was not realized. However, a book containing drawings by both artists was published after Klee passed away. It is an English edition of Novalis's *The Novices of Sais* published in 1949 by Curt Valentin,⁴⁹

who represented both artists in the United States (FIG. 11). It contains 60 drawings by Klee,⁵⁰ with a portrait of Novalis drawn by Masson on the frontispiece (FIG. 12).

Masson's frontispiece evokes the well-known portrait of Novalis by Friedrich Eduard Eichens. The minimalist lines capture the eyes and nose of the author. Around the face, the short lines swirl like a whirlwind, and the tiny circles and star-like symbols create a lively, light rhythm. The German Romantic poet Novalis and especially this book on the philosophy of nature must have meant a lot to Masson⁵¹ because he also contemplated throughout his life on the relationship between nature, animals, and humans, and sometimes represented aspects of their fusion. He read this book in 1938 in a French translation⁵² and expressed his deep empathy in a letter to Kahnweiler: “I do not think I have ever read anything that seems closer to my most profound thoughts.”⁵³

The coexistence of Klee and Masson in this book is a practical consequence of the circumstances surrounding the two artists: when Klee's art dealer produced the English edition of Novalis's work with illustrations by the artist, he chose for the

Fig. 11.1
Paul Klee, front cover of Novalis, *The Novices of Sais*, *Sixty Drawings by Paul Klee*, New York: Curt Valentin, 1949
© Zentrum Paul Klee, Bern, Image Archive

Fig. 11.2
Novalis, *The Novices of Sais*, *Sixty Drawings by Paul Klee*, New York: Curt Valentin, 1949, pp. 2–3
© Zentrum Paul Klee, Bern, Image Archive

Fig. 11.3
Novalis, *The Novices of Sais*, *Sixty Drawings by Paul Klee*, New York: Curt Valentin, 1949, pp. 26–27
© Zentrum Paul Klee, Bern, Image Archive

Fig. 12
 André Masson, frontispiece of Novalis, *The Novices of Sais, Sixty Drawings by Paul Klee*,
 New York: Curt Valentin, 1949
 © Zentrum Paul Klee, Bern, Image Archive

frontispiece a younger artist that he also dealt with – in fact, that artist admired both Klee and Novalis. Nevertheless, if we recall Masson’s text on Klee, the connection between the two artists appears essential and significant. We have found that: Masson states that Klee seeks the unlimited and has “a desire of infinir” of the romantics of the North.⁵⁴ Like Klee and the Northern romantics, Masson is also a seeker of “infinir.”

Kahnweiler, who understands the two painters, writes about them:

“While acknowledging the reality of the world he sees, he does not consider what he sees to be the ‘one and only world.’ For him the world is in perpetual flux. Here the romantic painter Klee links up with that other romantic André Masson who, in 1939, named one of the drawings of his ‘Mythology of Nature’: ‘There is no finished world.’”⁵⁵

Kahnweiler, using the term “romantic,” connects Klee and Masson. The affinity of the two artists is that they see the unfinished world in perpetual flux. He also finds another affinity between the two painters. In his text on Klee, he writes: “Paul Klee deals more with ‘forces’ than with ‘forms,’”⁵⁶ while in the text on Masson: “The universe of Masson is not a world of forms, like that of the cubists, but one of forces.”⁵⁷ He categorizes

Klee and Masson on the same side as those who deal with forces in flux and transformation.

CONCLUSION

We have discussed Masson’s discovery of Klee’s work and analysed Masson’s essay on Klee. In summary, Masson understands Klee’s art at the level of not only the creative process but also an essential question of what an artwork should be.

Indeed, Masson finds much in Klee: an attitude of turning his back on the conventions such as the traditional perspective system, or the “rules” of Cubism as well as the general perception of “smallness” or “weakness”; his specific concept of time; his attachment to his unique techniques, and the use of accidental nature in the creative process. It is notable also that Masson invents and uses the term “infinir” in his writing on Klee. Masson sees in Klee’s work a distinctive conception of time and understands his work as having the potential to transform. Furthermore, he projects his idea onto Klee – an idea that a work of art should not be static or fixed but has an energy that is constantly dynamic and ever-transforming.

In the text of Masson, “the Chinese” are mentioned in parallel with “certain romantics of North” as those who have a

desire to “infinir”: to let it never end. In this passage, we can find Masson’s original logic of identifying affinities between the West and the East and connecting them. Clarifying that affinity will be the next challenge. By the “Chinese” Masson alluded to the Zen monk painters of the Sung dynasty who made peculiar ink and wash paintings. Some of them splashed ink onto the support, without using brushes, by “spitting ink” or even throwing their colour-soaked caps on top of their paper or silk.”⁵⁸ Masson is fascinated with the Chinese Zen monk painters not only because of their free-spirited creation style but also because the lines and stains they accidentally marked on the supports appear to be a landscape with mountains, water, and wind. At this point, we cannot help but recall the words of Klee: “Art does not reproduce the visible but makes visible.”⁵⁹

¹ Breton 1988, p. 330.

² On the formation of the discourse of “Klee, Pioneer of Surrealism,” see Miyashita 2007. On the relationship between Klee and Surrealism, see Zentrum Paul Klee 2016.

³ Morando 2010, p. 40.

⁴ Miró 1977, p. 68.

⁵ The two painters worked in the adjacent studios from the end of 1921 to the end of 1925. Cf. Morando 2010, p. 38; Umland 1993, pp. 322–324.

⁶ “Ensemble, Masson et moi, nous avons découvert Paul Klee, découverte essentielle pour l’un et pour l’autre.” Miró 1995, p. 116.

⁷ Brassai 1982, p. 143. Photographer Brassai conveys Miró’s words.

⁸ Cf. Lanchner 1987, pp. 87–88; Temkin 1987, p. 24; Miyashita 2007, p. 138. Like Miró and Masson, Breton and the future Surrealists were interested in Hausenstein’s monograph. Max Ernst, who had already moved from Cologne to Paris and kept close contact with Breton, also mentions *Kairuan* in a request letter to Klee (dated 20 December, 1923). Cf. Miyashita 2007, p. 25.

⁹ Hausenstein 1921.

¹⁰ On Klee’s oil paint transfer drawings, see Kersten 2011.

¹¹ The gallery, founded by the Swiss gallery owner, art critic, and poet Max Eichenberger (Max Berger), hosted Klee’s first solo exhibition in Paris. Cf. Fuchs and Okuda 2016.

¹² Krauss 1972, pp. 13–14.

¹³ Cf. Krauss 1972; Temkin 1987.

¹⁴ Miyashita mentions that the early Surrealist poets around Breton were interested in Klee’s drawings because they saw the possibility of extending the “écriture automatique” into plastic arts. However, expressing agreement with Gertrude Graetz’s views, he also mentions a gap between the Surrealists’ automatism, which is free from the control of reason and logic and expresses unconscious desires, and the deliberate production seen in Klee’s work. Cf. Miyashita 2007, p. 5, 96.

¹⁵ Masson 1946.

¹⁶ Renne-Serbanne 1945.

¹⁷ Masson 1959.

¹⁸ Walter Pach translates this word as “primitives,” but here it should be translated as “romantics” to be more faithful to Masson’s original text.

¹⁹ Masson 1950a, unpaginated, translated by Walter Pach. For the original text, see Masson 1946, p. 106: “Henri Michaux, non sans humour, écrit des tableaux d’une école considérée jusqu’ici comme des plus émancipées à l’égard des servitudes visuelles que : ‘c’est bien connu, on n’y voit pas à plus de trois mètres.’ Tout au contraire, ce que recherche Klee, c’est l’illimité. Dès 1912, rejoignant à sa manière le désir d’infinir des Chinois et de certains romantiques du Nord, auxquels ses origines le rattachent, il veut tenir en échec le trop raisonnable horizon. La légère antenne d’un scarabée suffira pour mesurer le désert et le sillage d’un pollen humiliera la voie lactée.” Cf. Masson 1976, pp. 125–126.

²⁰ Lanchner 1987, p. 89.

²¹ Zentrum Paul Klee 2021.

²² Klee 1964, p. 228, no. 831.

²³ Masson 1950a, unpaginated. Cf. Masson 1946, pp. 105–106: “La critique, à son égard, est généralement embarrassée. Préférant l’éviter, on va jusqu’à arguer du format exigu de ses

- œuvres, jusqu'à prétendre : 'Ce ne sont là, que timbres-poste.' Mais justement Klee ne nous le cèle pas, il intitule une de ses œuvres – des plus caractéristiques : *Un petit monde*. Il n'eût pas été sensible à cet argument, (le timbre-poste) lui qui était de ceux qui pensent, avec William Blake, que l'énergie n'a que peu de rapports avec la dimension et qui sont prêts à affirmer que la méchanceté de la puce est telle qu'il en suffirait d'une ayant la taille d'un cheval pour ravager la Grande-Bretagne." Cf. Masson 1976, p. 125.
- ²⁴ Masson suggests Blake's tempera *The Ghost of a Flea* (c. 1819–20), small in size, measuring 21.4 cm by 16.2 cm. It is said that Blake once had a spiritual vision of a ghost of a flea. Cf. Tate.
- ²⁵ "Tels que *Petit Monde* (1914), œuvre exquise de sensibilité trahissant d'ailleurs son impuissance à fixer sa vision." Renne-Serbanne 1945, p. 675, note 2.
- ²⁶ "Il [=Klee] verse dans un véritable caricaturisme à rebours, saisissant des êtres et des choses non leur ligne de force, mais leur ligne de faiblesse." *Ibid.*, p. 672.
- ²⁷ Georges Bataille, who is close to Masson and has the idea of transgression, also expressed interest in Klee, stating that he has "the sweetness of vice." Cf. Bataille 1945/46, p. 52: "Klee, me semble-t-il, avait plutôt la douceur d'un vice."
- ²⁸ Masson 1950a, unpaginated. Cf. Masson 1946, p. 106: "son œuvre porte plus souvent l'empreinte des arts impériaux ou sacrés [...]. C'est que le monde de Klee se veut chargé de passé – un passé très lointain – [...]." Cf. Masson 1976, p. 125.
- ²⁹ Cf. Haxthausen 2012, p. 62. The author mentions regarding Klee's work: "While it appears materially old it is stylistically new [...]. His originality lay less in his choice of materials than in his manner of working with them."
- ³⁰ "Le goût très fin de Paul Klee pour l'aspect *usé, poncé, corrodé*. Ses œuvres, si personnelles, à peine sorties de ses mains il aime qu'elles ressemblent à des objets de fouille : vers l'anonymat. Ses œuvres, si novatrices, il désire qu'elles paraissent porter le poids des millénaires : Deux ou trois milles ans, voilà qui bonifie et *rajeunit* toutes choses. / Variante : Peintures aromatisées, macérées, embaumées ..." Masson 1959, p. 789.
- ³¹ Cf. Haxthausen 2000. The author finds in Klee's paintings "the simulated signs of old age and decay" and relates them to Alois Riegl's concept of "age value" (Alterswert) and Walter Benjamin's notion of "Aura."
- ³² Regarding Klee's conception of time: "the simultaneity of past and present" of his works, see Okuda and Kakinuma 2015, pp. 258–260.
- ³³ Cf. Kakinuma 2018, p. 141.
- ³⁴ The word "embaumées" in the original text has another notion of "embalmed," which might be said to be more related to ancient times. However, both notions are olfactory and have to do with transformation in some form.
- ³⁵ Klee 1964, p. 310, no. 941.
- ³⁶ Masson 1950a, unpaginated. Cf. Masson 1946, p. 107: "Paul Klee aura donc recours à des moyens personnels, alchimie qui lui appartient, ou emploiera les moyens de son temps pour exprimer cet espace délivré." Cf. Masson 1976, p. 126.
- ³⁷ Masson describes *Classic Coast* (*Klassische Küste*) as "an instant of perfection" and "a masterpiece" in Klee's pointillism. Cf. *ibid.*
- ³⁸ "[...] il [= Klee] la [= la technique] laisse alors agir à sa guise et renonce, par affection pour elle, à quelque autre perfection. Cela répond tout à fait à sa méthode de travail qui, certes, n'est pas une affaire de hasard, mais qui, sciemment, fait profit du hasard. Un défaut du papier, une particularité du fond de la peinture le mènent brusquement à un caprice grotesque, à une idée originale." Grohmann 1929, p. XVII.
- ³⁹ Cf. Levailant 1977, p. 478.
- ⁴⁰ Masson 1950b.
- ⁴¹ Kahnweiler 1950, p. 16.
- ⁴² Masson 1950a.
- ⁴³ On *Tériade* and *Verve*, see Paris 1973; *Tériade* 1996; Sfakianaki 2019.
- ⁴⁴ Letter from the *Revue Verve* (E. *Tériade*) to Paul Klee, 12.01.1938, Zentrum Paul Klee, Bern, Klee Family Donation, Inv. no. SFK Ko I Par 13.
- ⁴⁵ "Wie Sie sehen, bemühe ich mich sehr, Sie zu gewinnen – und dies im allgemeinen Interesse. T. [= *Tériade*] sagte mir auch, dass man sich

augenblicklich immer mehr für die deutschen 'Entarteten' interessiert (endlich einmal! –sage ich). In Amerika nämlich. Und dass die Zeit der deutschen Künstler in Amerika in bester Entwicklung ist. Nun wollen wir das Beste hoffen. Vom Pariser Interesse wird man nicht satt." Letter from Wassily Kandinsky to Paul Klee, 09.01.1938, Zentrum Paul Klee, Bern, Klee Family Donation, Inv. no. SFK Ko P Kan 40.

imbibé de couleurs à la tête de leur papier ou de leur soie." Masson 1956, p. 125.

⁵⁹ Klee, *Schriften*, p. 118.

⁴⁶ Tériade and Maurice Raynal occasionally signed their articles in *La Bête Noire* as "two blinds." Masson, exasperated, used the term literally, as "The Directors are two blinds," in a letter to Michel Leiris dated 17 June, 1935. Cf. Masson 1990, p. 256.

⁴⁷ In a letter to Kahnweiler dated 14 June 1935, Masson wrote about Tériade of Greek origin: "Poor Greek violated by the Surrealists." Cf. *ibid.*, p. 254.

⁴⁸ Bataille 1997, p. 327.

⁴⁹ Novalis 1949a.

⁵⁰ A German edition was published the same year. Most of the drawings are the same as seen in the US edition, but the page layout of each illustration is different. Cf. Novalis 1949b.

⁵¹ Masson also drew the Novalis cards in the Marseille Tarot Cards, a Surrealists' group work led by Breton (involving such painters as Victor Brauner, Max Ernst, and Wifredo Lam). Cf. Morando 2010, pp. 210–211, p. 215.

⁵² Armelle Guerne, poet and resistance activist, wanted to publish his translation with Masson's drawings; he, therefore, sent the manuscript to Masson. This French version came out in 1939 with a frontispiece by Masson but this is a different illustration from the US version. Cf. Novalis 1939.

⁵³ "Je crois que je n'ai jamais rien lu qui me semble plus proche de mes pensées les plus profondes." Letter from Masson to Kahnweiler, dated 10 April 1938, in: Masson 1990, p. 382.

⁵⁴ See note 19 of this paper.

⁵⁵ Kahnweiler 1950, p. 20.

⁵⁶ *Ibid.*, p. 16.

⁵⁷ Kahnweiler 1942, unpaginated.

⁵⁸ "[C]eux-ci [= des peintres bouddhistes des sectes *tch'an* ou *zen*] [...] ne dédaignaient pas de 'cracher l'encre' ou encore de jeter leur bonnet

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